

The thermal decomposition pattern of $\text{Ni}(\text{DPDTC})_2$ was different from other complexes and it proceeded through the formation of intermediate 1 : 1 complex, viz. $\text{Ni}.\text{DPDTC}$. Stoichiometry of this complex was confirmed by an independent chemical analysis of the sample. The weight of the final residue left at 750° almost corresponds with the weight expected for pure NiO .

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Rhenium. Part-XVIII. Isothiocyanato Complexes of Quadrivalent Rhenium

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THE present communication describes the reaction between $\text{K}_2[\text{ReI}_6]$ and KSCN in methanol in which two complex ions having essentially the same composition, viz. $[\text{Re}(\text{NCS})_6]^{2-}$ were obtained. While one of these has been fully characterised as hexaisothiocyanatorhenate(IV)^{1,2}, the other has been tentatively formulated as a dimer, $[\text{Re}_2(\text{NCS})_{12}]^{4-}$.

Experimental

A concentrated solution (60 ml) of $\text{K}_2[\text{ReI}_6]$ (3 g, 0.0029 mol) and excess of KSCN (3.6 g, 0.037 mol) in methanol (25 ml) was boiled for 0.5 h. The mixture was dried by evaporation, and then extracted with diethyl ether (75 ml) leaving a residue (~2 g). The extract was evaporated and dissolved in water (5 ml). The complex $\text{Cs}_2[\text{Re}(\text{NCS})_6]$ precipitated on addition of CsCl (5 g, 0.029 mol). The precipitate was washed with ice-cold water, extracted with acetone and the extract dried over fused calcium chloride. Elemental analysis (Table 1) gave Cs, Re and NCS ratio as 2 : 1 : 6.

$\text{Cs}_4[\text{Re}_2(\text{NCS})_{12}]$: The residue (~2 g) left after extraction with diethyl ether was dissolved in water (5 ml) and precipitated with CsCl (5 g, 0.029 mol). The precipitate was washed with ice-cold water followed by extraction with acetone and drying over fused calcium chloride. Elemental analysis (Table 1) gave Cs, Re and NCS ratio as 2 : 1 : 6. A thallium salt (Table 1) precipitated when a concentrated solution of the caesium salt (0.4 g, 0.00025 mol) was treated with TlNO_3 (0.4 g, 0.0015 mol) in water.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are dark red-brown, almost black. The two caesium salts are moderately soluble in methanol, ethanol and water, but highly soluble in acetone. The thallium salt is highly soluble in acetone, but insoluble in water, methanol and ethanol. The aqueous solutions of $\text{Cs}_2[\text{Re}(\text{NCS})_6]$ and $\text{Cs}_4[\text{Re}_2(\text{NCS})_{12}]$ appear reddish brown and brown black, respectively.

The room temperature magnetic moment value of $\text{Cs}_2[\text{Re}(\text{NCS})_6]$ (Table 1) agrees with those of other salts of $[\text{Re}(\text{NCS})_6]^{2-}$ reported earlier¹⁻³. The much lower magnetic moment values of $\text{Cs}_4[\text{Re}_2(\text{NCS})_{12}]$ and $\text{Tl}_4[\text{Re}_2(\text{NCS})_{12}]$ (Table 1) are indicative of their dinuclear nature involving thiocyanate bridging and/or Re—Re interaction, the latter being well known⁴ in Re^{III} and Re^{IV} .

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)				μ_{eff}^*	ν_{OH} cm^{-1}
	Re	S	N	Cs/Tl		
$\text{Cs}_2[\text{Re}(\text{NCS})_6]$	22.8 (23.3)	23.8 (24.0)	10.6 (10.5)	33.2 (33.2)	3.10	2 020
$\text{Cs}_4[\text{Re}_2(\text{NCS})_{12}]$	22.7 (23.3)	24.1 (24.0)	10.5 (10.5)	33.4 (33.2)	1.04 ^a	2 055
$\text{Tl}_4[\text{Re}_2(\text{NCS})_{12}]$	19.4 (19.7)	20.3 (20.4)	8.8 (8.9)	42.9 (43.3)	1.09 ^a	2 055

*At 298 K.

^aMagnetic moment per rhenium.

In the ir spectra (KBr), a very strong ν_{C-N} band was observed at $2\ 020\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{Cs}_2[\text{Re}(\text{NCS})_6]$ and at $2\ 055\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the two dinuclear complexes indicating that the complexes are most probably isothiocyanato ones^{1,2}. In ethanol medium, the cyanide band could be resolved in none of the complexes. This fact would favour the formulation $[(\text{SCN})_6\text{Re}-\text{Re}(\text{NCS})_6]^{4-}$ for the dinuclear complexes, since the presence of both bridging and terminal thiocyanate is likely to give more than one cyanide band.

The electronic spectra of $\text{Cs}_2[\text{Re}(\text{NCS})_6]$ in ethanol showed intense charge transfer bands at $38\ 600$ and $23\ 300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which agree with the earlier observations^{1,2}. The spectra of $\text{Cs}_2[\text{Re}_2(\text{NCS})_{12}]$, however, gave intense bands at $29\ 400$ and $22\ 900\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

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Diacido Complexes of Palladium(II) with Morpholine

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MORPHOLINE ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NO}$) is a potential nitrogen and oxygen donor ligand and its complexes with some transition metal ions are known¹⁻⁶. Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} complexes contain one and two ligand molecules³⁻⁶. In the bis-complexes, morpholine is bonded through N atom in chair form, while in mono complexes, it is a bridging ligand bonded to the metal atom through both nitrogen and oxygen atoms by retaining its chair conformation. The complexes of morpholine with platinum metals are not known in detail⁷. The platinum metal complexes are becoming important as anticancer agents⁸. The present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of palladium(II) complexes $[\text{Pd}(\text{L})_2(\text{X})_2]$, where L=morpholine; $\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- and SCN^- .

Experimental

$[\text{PdL}_2\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{X}=\text{Br}^-$, I^- , SCN^- or NO_2^-): An aqueous solution of palladium(II) chloride (0.001 mol in 50 ml) was treated with an excess of potassium salt of the requisite anion (in about 1 : 4 molar ratio) and warmed to get a clear solution. To the resulting solution morpholine (0.002 mol)

was added dropwise with stirring, when a cream or orange-yellow precipitate was formed. The precipitate was digested on a steam-bath for 0.5 h, and filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over fused CaCl_2 , (90–95%).

$[\text{PdL}_2\text{Br}_2]$ (light green form): The cream yellow variety of the dibromo complex (~5 g) was suspended in ethanol (50 ml) and morpholine (2 ml) and refluxed on a steam-bath for 2 h when the yellow compound was completely transformed to a light green product. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over fused CaCl_2 .

Chemical analysis (Table 1), electronic reflectance and ir spectra of the complexes were performed as reported earlier⁹.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF $[\text{PdL}_2\text{X}_2]$ COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)	
	M	N
$[\text{PdL}_2\text{Br}_2]$	23.96 (24.00)	06.38 (06.36)
$[\text{PdL}_2\text{I}_2]$	19.98 (19.85)	05.38 (05.24)
$[\text{PdL}_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	26.99 (26.79)	14.72 (14.62)
$[\text{PdL}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	27.35 (27.41)	15.12 (15.05)

Results and Discussion

The interaction of morpholine with palladium(II) gave only bis-complexes, $[\text{PdL}_2\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- or SCN^-). The dihalo complexes dissolve in excess of morpholine in aqueous solution but attempts to get solid complexes were unsuccessful. The cream-yellow dibromo, $[\text{PdL}_2\text{Br}_2]$ complex on prolonged refluxing in ethanol with excess of morpholine changed to a light green isomeric product. However, the isomeric products could not be isolated with other diacido complexes. The diacido complexes are insoluble in water, methanol and ethanol but dissolved in dimethylformamide and pyridine. The complexes were diamagnetic. The solid state reflectance spectra of the complexes displayed a medium band or shoulder in the region 390–430 nm. The green dibromo complex displayed this band at 420 nm while λ_{max} of the yellow product was at 400 nm. The absorption bands were assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transition, usually observed in the square-planar palladium(II) complexes¹⁰.

The ν_{N-H} of the free ligand ($3\ 300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) shifted to lower frequency by $130 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and δ_{NH} of ligand ($1\ 455\text{ cm}^{-1}$) by $5-10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in almost all the complexes, indicating the bonding of morpholine through nitrogen atom¹¹. The sharp ν_{C-O-O} bands